

The first records of *Calamobius filum* (Rossi, 1790) and *Theophilea subcylindricollis* Hladil, 1988 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiini) from Kyiv Region, Ukraine

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Gubin, O. I. & Pljushtch, I. G. The first records of *Calamobius filum* (Rossi, 1790) and *Theophilea subcylindricollis* Hladil, 1988 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiini) from Kyiv Region, Ukraine. Summary. The longhorn beetles *Calamobius filum* (Rossi, 1790) and *Theophilea subcylindricollis* Hladil, 1988 are found in Kyiv Region, Ukraine for the first time. Materials were collected in May-June 2018. The present distribution areas of both species are briefly characterized.

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Calamobius filum*, *Theophilea subcylindricollis*, Kyiv Region, Ukraine, first record.

Губін, О. І. і Плющ, І. Г. Перші знахідки *Calamobius filum* (Rossi, 1790) і *Theophilea subcylindricollis* Hladil, 1988 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiini) в Київській області, Україна. Резюме. Жуки-вусачі *Calamobius filum* (Rossi, 1790) і *Theophilea subcylindricollis* Hladil, 1988 вперше знайдені в Київській області, Україна. Матеріал було зібрано у травні-червні 2018. Стисло охарактеризовані сучасні ареали обох видів.

Ключові слова: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, *Calamobius filum*, *Theophilea subcylindricollis*, Київська область, Україна, перша знахідка.

Introduction

Calamobius filum (Rossi, 1790) and *Theophilea subcylindricollis* Hladil, 1988 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lamiini) are the xerothermophilous species of longhorn beetles, that initially was known only from Southern and Southern-East regions of Ukraine (Bartenev, 2009). Since 2010s it is noticed expanding of this species areal to the wood-and-steppe and forest zones (Zamoroka, 2017). In 2018, the mass invasion of *C. filum* and *T. subcylindricollis* was firstly recorded in Kyiv Region.

Material and methods

The materials were collected by entomological sweep-net in May-June 2018. The photographs were taken using a Zeiss AxioCam Erc 5s camera, mounted on Carl Zeiss Stemi 2000-C binocular microscope with Zen 2012 (blue edition) software package. Nomenclature of taxa follows the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera (Löbl & Smetana, 2010) with additions and changes by Danilevsky (2018). All the specimens from this study are deposited in personal collections of authors (Kyiv & Donetsk, Ukraine).

Results

Calamobius filum (Rossi, 1790) (Figs 1–2)

Material examined: Ukraine: Kyiv Region, Obukhiv Distr., Pidhirtsi vill. env., 50.1400°N 30.3207°E, 27.05.2018, 11 spec. (I. G. Pljushtch); idem, 01.06.2018, 16 spec. (I. G. Pljushtch); idem, 07.06.2018, 9 spec. (I. G. Pljushtch).

Xerothermophilous Circummediterranean species, that widespread in Central and Southern Europe, North Africa, Near East, Asia Minor and Caucasus (Bartenev, 2009; Zamoroka & Mateleshko, 2016). In Europe *C. filum* initially was distributed mainly on the territory of the Southern Europe, but since 2010s its expansion of its distribution northward is being recorded (Zamoroka, 2017). The species has been recorded from following countries: **Europe:** Albania, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, European Turkey, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Macedonia, Malta, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (South of European part), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine; **Africa:** Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia; **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Armenia, Cyprus, Georgia, North Iran, Israel, Jordan,

Figs 1–2. *Calamobius flum*, habitus: 1 — male; 2 — female.

Lebanon, Syria, Turkey (Zamoroka & Mateleshko, 2016; Danilevsky, 2018).

In Ukraine *C. flum* initially was known from Dnipropetrovsk Region, Kherson Region, and Crimea (Bartenev, 2009; Bartenev & Terekhova, 2011; Zamoroka & Mateleshko, 2016), but in 2015–2016 its mass invasion was registered in the Carpathian-Podillya region, and its wide distribution in the wood-and-steppe zone of all of Ukraine up to 50° of North was predicted (Zamoroka & Mateleshko, 2016).

In 2018, the mass invasion of *C. flum* was firstly recorded in Kyiv Region near the southern boundary of Kyiv (Obukhiv Distr.).

Theophilea subcylindricollis Hladil, 1988 (Figs 3–4)

Material examined: Ukraine: Kyiv Region, Obukhiv Distr., Pidhirtsi vill. env., 50.1400°N 30.3207°E, 10.05.2018, 12 spec. (I. G. Pljushch); idem, 27.05.2018, 24 spec. (I. G. Pljushch); idem, 01.06.2018, 70 spec. (I. G. Pljushch); idem, 07.06.2018, 7 spec. (I. G. Pljushch); Kyiv, Bykivnia vill. env., 50.2834°N 30.3942°E, 15–21.05.2018, 10 spec. (I. G. Pljushch).

Xerothermophilous species that initially occurred in Pannonian and North Ponticus Basins (Bartenev, 2009; Zamoroka, 2017). Since 2000's its is expanding distribution westward, northward, and eastward. Now the species is registered in Czech Republic, Hungary,

Macedonia, Moldova, Romania, Russia (from sentral and southern regions of European Territory to Southern Ural Mountains), Serbia, Slovakia, Ukraine, and Kazakhstan (Bartenev, 2009; Zamoroka, 2017; Danilevsky, 2018).

In Ukraine, *T. subcylindricollis* previously was known only from Southern and Southern-East regions (Mykolaiv Region, Kherson Region, Dnipropetrovsk Region, Donetsk Region, Luhansk Region) (in some cases was misidentified and reported as “*Theophilea cylindricollis* Pic, 1895”) (Bartenev, 2004, 2009; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004; Bartenev & Terekhova, 2011; Andrushevych, 2014; Zamoroka, 2017). It is worth noting that in Donetsk and Luhansk Regions, the species is numerous and is found through the all region (Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004). *Theophilea subcylindricollis* is absent in Crimea (Bartenev, 2009; Bartenev & Terekhova, 2011), but Zamoroka notes Crimea as the part of initial areal (Zamoroka, 2017). In 2004 *T. subcylindricollis* was firstly registered in Kharkiv Region, and now it has become a common species (Bartenev & Terekhova, 2006). In 2016–2017 the mass invasion of *T. subcylindricollis* was observed into Carpathian-Podillya region (Zamoroka & Kapelyukh, 2016; Zamoroka, 2017).

In 2018, the mass invasion of *T. subcylindricollis* was recorded in Kyiv Region near the southern border of Kyiv (Obukhiv Distr.) as well as within the city (Desnianskyi Distr.).

Figs 3–4. *Theophilea subcylindricollis*, habitus: 3 — male; 4 — female.

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